

First Vizslas of Canada: Before 1969 AD

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Author Note

This paper is a continuation of previously published studies on the Vizsla breed history (Moshynska, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14852820>; Moshynska, 2020, <https://www.ancient-origins.net/history-ancient-traditions/vizsla-0013289>; Moshynska, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14903342>).

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Abstract

The Vizsla (Smooth), also referred to as a Hungarian Pointer, Magyar Vizsla, or Magyar Pointer, is a beautiful, noble-looking, intelligent, and versatile breed excelling at various tasks presented to them. Vizsla may become a hunter, show prospect, competitive or non-competitive performance sport athlete, or simply a companion. Such versatility is due to hundreds years of selective breeding and betterment of the breed, its traits and abilities. This paper reviews the newsletter and other archival records between 1850 and 1969 that cover stories about the first Vizslas in Canada.

First Vizslas of Canada: Before 1969 AD

Background

In this paper, the author summarizes the newspaper and other archival records and fills the existing gaps in the Canadian (early years) history of the Vizsla (Smooth) breed. According to the Vizsla Canada (n.d.), the first Vizslas set their feet on Canada's soil in Ontario in 1955. It was Ben Jones of St. Catharines, Ontario, who brought into Canada three Vizslas. The author of this paper, however, came across newspaper and archival records mentioning Vizslas in Canada at an earlier date (The Globe and Mail, 1953).

The aims of this study were: 1) capture archived stories about early Vizslas in Canada, 2) create a reference list of the newspaper and other archived articles covering the Vizsla subject from the earliest available Canadian records and until 1969, and 3) seek the evidence of any Vizslas possibly entering the country earlier than 1955. Thanks to the open access to information movement and the digitization efforts, millions of records became part of various digital repositories around the globe. The author of this paper reviewed the digitized newspaper and other records in various repositories including the ProQuest Historical Newspapers, The Vizsla News Archive of the Vizsla Club of America, Vizsla Canada Archive, Wikipedia Online Newspaper Archives, Google News Archive, and Newspapers.com. The author set the search period from 1850 to 1969, conducted the research between October 4, 2018 and February 26, 2023, and used the following keywords: Vizsla, Hungarian Pointer, Magyar Vizsla, and Magyar Pointer, as well as Canada. The author presented some of these findings as a part of her Master of Management in Library and Information studies at the University of Southern California (class of 2022) and in previous publications (Moshynska, 2019; Moshynska, 2020; Moshynska, 2023). Whenever possible, the author of this paper described findings in a chronological order and grouped by topics and included links to relevant archived articles. Additional Information included in footnotes.

First Vizslas of Canada

Pre-1953 Years

The author found hunting with pointers in Canada first mentioned in 1827 (Montreal Gazette, 1827). The spike in Canadian newspapers covering field trialing with dogs began around April 24, 1886 when the Manitoba Field Trial Club¹ was formed in Winnipeg (Manitoba Free Press, 1886). However, prior to 1955, the Canadian newspaper records referenced other pointing breeds taking part in the field trials that included Setters and Pointers, including lemon- and lemon/white-colored, but no Vizslas.

The Western part of Canada had a large number of game birds (The Globe and Mail, 1959; Dawson, 1959; The Vancouver Sun, 1962) and thus was attractive to those hunting and field trialing with pointing dogs. The May 27, 1933 issue of The Winnipeg Evening Tribune ran a story about the Hungarians settling in Manitoba since 1880s. They talked about the first Magyar Parliament that was on the banks of Danube today, founded back in 1222, so Hungarians in Canada were called the “Britishers of the Danube Valley” (p. 5). The article identified that by 1933, there were about two thousands Hungarians living in Manitoba, with about hundred thousand in total residing in Canada.

A Vizsla named Zsoka, who was reported hunting in 1938 on Michael Kende’s estate, was first sold to Pulitzer, USA, and later – to friends in Canada (The Vizsla News, 1960, August-September, p. 8). Another Vizsla named Dendi also ended up in Canada, after appearing with Amory Ryan in the April 8, 1940 issue of the Life magazine (The Vizsla News, 1960, August-September, 1960). Many more Hungarians arrived after the 1956 revolution in Hungary (The Winnipeg evening Tribune, 1959).

¹ Manitoba Field Trial Club was formed at the meeting that took place in the office of C. A. Boxer at 4 Portage Avenue in Winnipeg (Manitoba Free Press, 1886).

The Windsor Star, an Ontario-based newspaper, on April 29, 1952, published a photograph of Sari and Rex and their first litter of six Vizsla puppies born in The United States, signaling a new era in the North American Vizsla world.

1953-1955

Canadian newspapers started talking about Vizsla in the early 1950th. The Globe and Mail devoted several articles to Vizsla. On January 24, 1953, The Globe and Mail educated the public on how to pronounce “Vizsla” - it is “vish-la” – and that the plural for Vizsla would be “Vizslak” (p. 26). (In this paper, the author uses plural Vizslas as this has become generally accepted.) “The Hungarians having sent us a few dogs in recent years there is now a chance for a little more confusion. “One Pull, small sheep dog, but two Pulik. The Vizsla, a pointer, is pronounced vish-la, and if you have two of them they’re Vizslak” (The Globe and Mail, 1959). Vizsla breed was seeing as a saver of the Weimaraner breed: “Fortunately for the Weimaraner, the Vizsla, which is very similar except that it is Hungarian in origin rather than German, came along before the breed was completely ruined by puppy factories and breeders who hadn’t the foggiest idea what the dog was supposed to do.” (The Globe and Mail, 1960).

On May 14, 1955, The Vancouver Sun published a short article about Vizsla that “points his nose at birds ..., efficient at all animal trailing, night-trailing and guard work..., [has] a gentle, tractable mien..., accomplished retriever, fearless of water and developed by noble hunters of yore” (p. 22). The Vizsla described as the one smarter than the German Shorth-Haired Pointer and the Weimaraner, slower in the field than the English Pointer, and “a bit flashier” than the German Short-haired Pointer or the Weimaraner (p. 22). This article also mentioned F. S. Verrall of Redmond, just outside Seattle breeding Vizslas around the time of the article publication.

Though there are slight discrepancies about when exactly the first Vizslas arrived in Canada, all sources seem to agree the first Vizslas arrived between 1953 and 1955. Ed McKoy

(also referred to as McCoy), a resident of Hamilton in Ontario, imported a male Vizsla named *Gay V Schloss Loosdorf*. This Vizsla was born on August 1, 1953 (Vizsla Database, n.d.) and he was registered in the Field Dog Stud Book in 1953 (Coffman, 1991). His sire *Gingo V Schloss Loosdorf* and dam *Hera V Schloss Loosdorf* were both from Austria, both were also descendants of *Panni XV* and *Betyar*. *Gay V Schloss Loosdorf*, however, has no known history of mating or any offspring left (Vizsla Database, n.d.). According to Strauz and Cunningham (1973), J. Ben Jones (St. Catharines, Ontario) imported three Vizslas to Canada in 1955. However, he did not breed any of these dogs (Straus & Cunningham, 1973).

These first imports all arrived from the United States (Vizsla Database, n.d.) and had Czechoslovakian, Hungarian, or Austrian origin. In addition to *Gay V Schloss Loosdorf*, there were *Happy V Schloss Loosdorf*², *Heidi V Schloss Loosdorf*, *Roth V Dravavolgy*, and *Mida Selle Povazia* (Vizsla Database, n.d.)

First Vizslas Born on the Canadian Soil

March 20, 1956 marked a crucial milestone in the Canadian history of the Vizsla when *Heidi v Schloss Loosdorf* delivered her first and only litter of six puppies out of *Alcon V Schloss Loosdorf*³ (Vizsla Database, n.d.), named *Etza*, *Chief*, *Rudolph*, *Bruno's V Schloss Loosdorf*, *Eric V Schloss Loosdorf*, and *Major V Schloss* (Vizsla Database, n.d.). These puppies were bred by Oliver R. Hoare, Dalgreig Kennels in Dauphin, Manitoba, and advertised as from the proven in the field, kind, and friendly parents (The Calgary Herald, 1956, 1957). Other Western Canada newspapers ran this kennel's ads as well (Edmonton Journal, 1956; The Leader Post, 1956). On November 22, 1956, the same Manitoba kennel advertised a sale of Vizsla puppies

² *Happy V Schloss Loosdorf*, a male born on February 7, 1954, had at least 7 offspring; *Heidi V Schloss Loosdorf*, a female born on April 13, 1954, had 6 offspring; *Roth V Dravavolgy*, a male born on July 18, 1954, had no known offspring left; and *Mida Selle Povazia*, a female born on May 12, 1955, had at least 2 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

³ *Alcon V Schloss Loosdorf*, a male born in The United States on October 14, 1952 (Sire: Rex Del Gelsomino and Dam: Gelse V Schloss Loosdorf), who had 58 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

“of proven hunters” with a sire placing second in the field trial (Edmonton Journal, 1956, p. 27).

On August 14, 1958, The Montreal Star advertised Vizsla puppies available in Quebec.

Alberta and British Columbia were not far behind Manitoba and Quebec. In 1959, Boreas Kennels Reg. in Carbon, Alberta advertised six-month-old Vizsla puppies, as the ones with “excellent nose” and as “excellent retrievers” (Edmonton Journal, 1959, p. 35).

“First litter in Edmonton” “from best Hungarian bloodline” was advertised in Edmonton Journal in 1964. “Hungarian Vizsla Import 1st in British Columbia” ad appeared in The Vancouver Sun in January 1959 (p. 36). Alfred J. Sullivan’s litter announcement and a picture of eight one-month old Vizsla hunting puppies appeared in 1959 in The Province, a newspaper published in Richmond, British Columbia.

Recognition by the Canadian Kennel Club in 1958

Prior to 1958, the Hungarian Vizsla could only compete in the miscellaneous class (The Windsor Star, 1956). The Vizsla (Smooth) breed earned the recognition from the Canadian Kennel Club in 1958, who recognized the breed in 1960, two years ahead of the American Kennel Club. A. G. Gerle (or Guerle, Puszta Kennels Reg'd in Montreal, Quebec) is credited for his efforts in promoting the breed and its work in the field to generate sufficient interest to get the breed recognized in Canada (Strauz & Cunningham, 1973). In the March 1960 issue of The Vizsla News, A. Gerle received a credit and Board nomination for the Vizsla Club (in the United States) for his promotion of the breed leading to the recognition by the Canadian Kennel Club (pp. 2-3).

In the Fall of 1957, A.G.Gerle brought two Vizslas from Czechoslovakia (referred to specific countries as to Czech Republic or Slovakia after Czechoslovakia was dissolved on December 31, 1992) (Coffman, 1991; Gerle, 1958). One of them was a Vizsla male named *Can*

*Ch Agres Z Povazia*⁴, bred by Koloman Slimak (Povazia Z kennel) that became the first CKC-registered Vizsla. The other Vizsla was *Can Ch Lyska Z Tattier*. Both puppies had complete six-generation pedigrees and shipped by air to Montreal in a box classified as “very sharp”(Gerle, 1958, p.17).

First Vizsla Wins in the Show Ring

These two dogs, Agres and Lyska were the first two Vizslas shown in Canada as a recognized breed (Strauz & Cunningham, 1973). A. Gerle’s interview and a photo of both dogs appeared in the April 26, 1958 issue of Samedi-Dimanche. The historical event for both dogs, handled by A. Gerle, as they appeared in the show ring, was on April 27, 1958 at the Ladies Kennel Club Show in Montreal, Quebec under Judge Robert McCandless of New York, NY. (Cook, 1958). *Can Ch Agres Z Povazia*, pictured in The Montreal Star on April 28 that year, became the first Vizsla to take Best of Breed and the first Canadian show Champion on record (Cook, 1958, p. 22). In 1959, *Can Ch Lyska Z Tattier* became the second bench Champion in Canada (Strauz & Cunningham, 1973). Dr. Adalbert (also known as William, Bill or Bela) and Elizabeth Kemenes-Kettner bought both Vizslas, *Can Ch Agres Z Povazia* and *Can Ch Lyska Z Tattier*, from A. Gerle, and established the Bakony Kennel Ltd. in Alberta (Strauz & Cunningham, 1973).

On February 20, 1960, a Vizsla appeared in a show ring for the first time in the Western Canada, in Calgary (The Calgary Herald, 1960).

Vizslas continued to do well in the show ring earning group placements (Nicholson, 1962; The Ottawa Journal, 1965; Times Colonist, 1962), including winning the entire Sporting Group (Nicholson, 1962; The Ottawa Journal, 1965). The first win of the Sporting Group in North

⁴ *Agres Z Povazia* (Sire: *Ago vom Arpadvar* and Dam: *Astra Olca*), male born on August 10, 1957 in Czechoslovakia, sired at least 64 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.); *Lyska Z Tattier*, female born in Czechoslovakia on June 19, 1957 (Sire: *Ajax Olca* and Dam: *Katka Z Tattier*, bred by I.J. Gajdos, Tattier Z), had at least 21 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.)

America was in May 1962 in Nanaimo, British Columbia. A few newspapers covered this first ever group win, which occurred not once but twice during the same weekend - on May 13 and 14. The Sporting Group winner was a Vizsla named *Am/Can Ch Souvenir Csabe Lidi*⁵ that was bred by F. S. Verrall and owned by Roy Geil of Kingston, Washington (Nicholson, 1962; The Vizsla News, 1963, July, p.7). This Vizsla's photo appeared in the Vizsla News' February 1964 issue (p. 10). Kemenes-Kettners' Vizsla named *Prucsok (Can Ch Aprod Prucsok*⁶, bred by Karoly Fuzek in Hungary) was the second Vizsla winning the Sporting Group in North America. This was on February 23, 1963, at the all-breed 10th Alberta Kennel Club show in Edmonton, Alberta (American Kennel Gazette, 1963). The third Sporting Group winner in 1965 in Ottawa was *Am/Can Ch Janoras Pawlane Suntan*⁷, owned by Dr. Phil A. Wright of Guelph, Ontario and bred by John Janora of West Seneca, New York. Suntan finished his show Championship title that year.

The breeding of Suntan and *Bakony Csikcsicsoi Boske*⁸ resulted in the birth of the first Canadian and American Best in Show winner and American-Canadian-Mexican Champion, named Danny, *Am/Can/Mex/Int Ch Napkeltei Vadasz Dalos*⁹, as well as his sibling *Can Ch Napkeltei Vadasz Darazs* (Strauz & Cunningham, 1973). Dr. Wright's *Am/Can Ch Napkeltei Vadasz Hiros*¹⁰, a half-sibling of Danny and Darazs, went to live with Nick and Jean Reagan in Ottawa (The Montreal Star, 1971).

⁵ *Souvenir Csabe Lidi* (also known as *Sue Csabe Lidi*), a female born in The United States on July 17, 1957 (Sire: *Buck Selle* and Dam: *Sona Selle*) with no known offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

⁶ *Aprod Prucsok*, a male born in Hungary on June 21, 1961 (Sire: *Cezar (MV)* and Dam: *Arokparti Zengo*) with at least 61 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

⁷ *Janoras Pawlane Suntan*, a male born in The United States on June 10, 1961 (Sire: *Kelly of Gardenville* and Dam: *Star of Gardenville*) and imported to Canada, who had 127 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

⁸ *Bakony Csikcsicsoi Boske*, a male born in Canada on May 29, 1963 (Sire: *Aprod Prucsok* and Dam: *Arokparti Parazs*) had at least 7 offspring of the same sire, Suntan (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

⁹ *Napkeltei Vadasz Dalos*, a male born in Canada on February 22, 1966 (Sire: *Janoras Pawlane Suntan* and Dam: *Bakony Csikcsicsoi Boske*), who had 57 offspring.

Napkeltei Vadasz Darazs, a male born in Canada on February 22, 1966 (Sire: *Janoras Pawlane Suntan* and Dam: *Bakony Csikcsicsoi Boske*), who had 54 offspring.

¹⁰ *Napkeltei Vadasz Hiros*, a male born in Canada on May 16, 1967 (Sire: *Janoras Pawlane Suntan* and Dam: *Napkeltei Zsuka V Hunt*), who had at least 7 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

The winner of the 1967 Vizsla National Specialty, which was held on August 27, 1967 at the Chagrin Valley Kennel Club in Chagrin Falls in Ohio, was from Canada. The winner was a Vizsla male named Jonish or Joni (*Am/Can Ch Count Jonish Mignotte*¹¹), bred by Alex and Marion De Liphay of La Canada, California and owned by Elizabeth Mignotte of Exeter, Ontario (The Vizsla News, 1967, August-September). The Judge Cecil Y. Smith of Palmyra, New York received ovations when made the final pick (p. 13). A photo of Elizabeth Mignotte and her American and Canadian Champion Vizsla Joni appeared in the October 1967 issue of The Vizsla News (p. 11). Joni's photo also was on a cover page of the January 1968 issue of The Vizsla News.

Vizslas of the Bakony Kennel

In 1952, Dr. Bela (or Albert, Adalbert, or Bela) Kemenes-Kettner (or Kemenes) and Elizabeth Kemenes-Kettner emigrated from Hungary to Canada. Dr. Kemenes, who was 40 years of age at that time and had a double doctorate in law and political sciences, reported starting his career from the beginning in Canada (The Calgary Herald, 1953). He first washed dishes in a Montreal restaurant, then worked as a foreman in an airplane factory and at the Imperial Oil Ltd. Later, he moved to Calgary, where he delivered The Herald newspaper during the day and cleaned a hotel at night. Also, he coached the Hungarian soccer team in Calgary. The family's first Vizsla was named *Greta Selle Karpat*¹² (Coffman, 1991).

Later, Dr. Kemenes-Kettners bought from A. Gerle two Vizslas, *Can Ch Agres Z Povazia* (Agres) and *Can Ch Lyska Z Tattier* (Lyska), and moved with them from Montreal to Calgary - Forest Lawn in Alberta (The Calgary Herald, 1960). Kemenes-Kettners established kennels west of the Silver Springs Rd., "specializing in the hunting strain...Hungarian Vizslas, English

¹¹ *Count Jonish Mignotte*, a male born in The United States on July 16, 1963 (Sire: Herzog Schloss Loosdorf and Dam: Fruska Kisfaludi), who had 21 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

¹² *Greta Selle Karpat*, a female born in The United States on June 2, 1958 (Sire: Buck Selle and Dam: Greta Z Karpat), who had at least 18 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

Setters, Irish Setters, and Cocker Spaniels.” (Calgary Herald, 1964). Agres and Lyska, pictured in the April 14, 1960 issue, were described as “first of their kind in Western Canada” (The Calgary Herald, 1960, p. 19).

The Bakony Kennel was successful and produced many champions (Strauz & Cunningham, 1973). *Can Ch Lyska Z Tattier* and *Can Ch Agres Z Povazia* bred several times; they had 21 puppies together (Vizsla Database, n.d.). Agres had seven mating partners and 64 puppies in total during his lifetime (The Bakony and Budavary kennels).

A 22-month-old Vizsla named Jolla (*Vizsta’s Jolla*¹³) became the first female Vizsla to win Best in Show in North America. Jolla won under Judge Ed Dixon, at the Evergreen Kennel Club show in Vancouver, British Columbia on March 8, 1980. She was bred by Beryl K Taylor in Spokane, Washington and owner-handled by Vaughn Franske of Coquitlam, British Columbia (The Vizsla News, 1980). Vaughn Franske was the second owner of Jolla.

Approximately a year later and after acquiring their first Vizslas in Canada, Kemenes-Kettners (Vizsla Canada Archives, n.d.) exported from Hungary to Canada another female Vizsla named Parazs – *Can Ch Arokparti Parazs*¹⁴, who was bred by Szabo Martonne. Later her ownership was transferred to Charles and Joan Hunt (Vizsla Database, n.d.). Together with Szalay Miklos, Kemenes-Kettners imported from Hungary another female named Tincsi – *Can Ch Egerhegyi Tincsi*¹⁵, who was bred by Gustav Rudlof. Dr. Kemenes-Kettner reported the arrival of Tincsi, as “fully trained” Vizsla (The Vizsla News, 1963, March, p. 3). Tincsi (also referred to as Trincsi) had 29 offspring (The Bakony and Kutya kennels) with three mating partners (Vizsla Canada archives, n.d.).

¹³ *Vizsta’s Jolla*, a female born in The United States on April 14, 1978 (Sire: *Vizsta’s Magnum Ryder* and Dam: *Vizsta’s Inga Krishna*) had 23 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

¹⁴ *Arokparti Parazs*, a female born in Hungary on October 28, 1959 (Sire *Csikcsicsoi Aprod* and Dam: *Kati*), who had 31 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

¹⁵ *Egerhegyi Tincsi*, a female born in Hungary on May 26, 1960 (Sire: *Csikcsicsoi Aprod* and Dam: *Divat Tucso*), who had 29 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

The Bakony Kennel produced many prize-winning Canadian Vizslas (Coffman, 1991). On July 5, 1962, the Whitehorse Daily Star covered a story on a Vizsla named Csoda, owned by Ted Lattin of Whitehorse and handled by Dr. Kemenes-Kettner. At that time, Csoda was on her summer circuit trip for one more winner's ribbon to complete her Grand Championship.

Kemenes-Kettners' *Can Ch Aprod Prucsock* and *Bakony Zengo V Hunt*¹⁶ reported completing their championships at the Alberta Kennel Club show in Edmonton in February 1963. A photo of Elizabeth Kemenes-Kettner stacking Prucsock with a Judge presenting Prucsock with the Sporting Group win published in the May issue of The Vizsla News (p. 9).

By 1964, Kemenes-Kettners's four-year-old Tincsi and two-year-old Pushi (*Can Ch Devecseri Somloi Pushi*¹⁷) achieved higher titles in both, the show and the field work. "Tincsi, imported from Hungary, has three field winner championships to her credit and has been named show Champion at Calgary and Edmonton shows," Elizabeth Kemenes-Kettner told in her interview to the Calgary Herald in 1964 (Hehr, 1964). "And Pushi has three first place awards, ten group places, five seconds and two fourth place ribbons to his credit," she continued about her other own Vizsla named Pushi (Hehr, 1964). Handled by Elizabeth Kemenes-Kettner, Pushi won the Sporting Group at the Alberta Kennel Club's show in Edmonton in February 1965 (The Calgary Herald, 1965), and placed in groups seven out of nine times entered in the show (The Vizsla News, 1964, June, p. 6). In 1966, Pushi's photo appeared in a newspaper once again, as he continued winning major prizes in a show ring (The Calgary Herald, 1966).

It appears that at some point, Dr. Bela Kemenes-Kettner moved to Ontario. An obituary of Dr. Adalbert (Bela) Kemenes-Kettner appeared in the June 6, 1998 issue of The Standard. In this obituary he is referred to as a father and step-father, as well as husband and grandfather of

¹⁶ *Bakony Zengo V Hunt*, a female born in The United States on October 8, 1961 (Sire: Almos and Dam: Kincsem V Hunt), who had 14 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

¹⁷ *Devecseri Smnloi Pushi*, a male born in Canada on September 27, 1962 (Sire: Aprod Prucsock and Dam: Bakony Somloi Szende), who had 40 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

seven grandchildren and one great-grandchild. He died on June 4, 1998, at age of 87, at the Hotel Dieu Hospital. His funeral was at the Patrick J. Darte Funeral Chapel, and he was buried at St. John's Cemetery (St. Catharines, Lincoln, Ontario) (The Standard, 1998).

Elizabeth Kemenes-Kettner appeared in the Edmonton Journal on October 21, 2007 when her family celebrating her 87th birthday. Several months later, on April 4, 2008, she was reported to have passed away, after a lengthy illness, in the Youville Hospital in Edmonton (The Edmonton Journal, 2008). The celebration of her life took place on May 2, 2008 at Serenity Funeral Service.

Dr. Kemenes-Kettner's contribution to the Vizsla world is well recorded. However, Elizabeth Kemenes-Kettner's contribution to the breed's history is yet to be fully recognized. Calgary Herald's article (1964, November) shed some light on Elizabeth's role, "From 7 a.m. to late evening she knows nothing but dogs", "all 50 of her charges" (p. 35). Elizabeth testified, "BUT I DO most of the work" as her husband Bill was busy with other things, she told a reporter (p. 35). Elizabeth's role included feeding and grooming the dogs, cleaning their kennels, and training them for shows (p. 35).

In June 2019, the author showed her own Vizsla named Hera (*Can GChEx, RCh Vizslavilla Prize Pure Goddess*) in Cold Lake, Alberta, when a lady in a black t-shirt with an image of a dog skeleton and the writing "In dog years, I'm dead", asked me if I knew Elizabeth Kemenes-Kettner. (Sadly, the author did not as she joined the Vizsla world after E. Kemenes-Kettner's passing.) Anita Johnston, who gave the author permission to publish their conversation, worked as a show secretary for over half of the century and remembered Elizabeth Kemenes-Kettner well. She recalled, Elizabeth lived in a small town called Coronado just outside of St. Albert, Alberta, loved dogs, was fascinated by babies, and loved to hold them all. Johnston recalled Elizabeth was the one (and not Bill) who always showed her Vizslas in

Alberta, in 1960s and 1970s, confirming what Elizabeth Kemenes-Kettner told The Calgary Herald back in 1964.

Number of Vizslas Growing in Canada

By 1960, there was a spike in the registrations of the purebred dogs. Approximately nine million registrations (with an annual intake of a half million) were completed by AKC, and 350,000 registrations – by CKC; double the numbers since 1954 (The Globe Magazine, 1960).

The July 4, 1959 issue of The Province published a photo of eight Vizsla puppies bred by Alfred J. Sullivan, residing at 712 Miller Road in Richmond, British Columbia. A Vizsla, “newest sensation” (The Province, 1959, p. 32) and “a rare European hunting dog”, was shown for the first time in Western Canada in Calgary in 1960 (The Calgary Herald, 1960, p.34).

Around this time, Dr. Phil A. Wright founded his Napkelte Kennel and brought a Vizsla named Suntan (*Am/Can Ch Janoras Pawlane Suntan*) from John Janora of West Seneca, New York (Coffman, 1991; Sirauz & Cunningham, 1973). (P. Wright imported another fifteen dogs from Hungary and the U.S. within the next few years.) Others joined the Vizsla breeding efforts (Coffman, 1991). Among breeders who appeared in newspapers were Wes and Dorothy Basler of St. Vital, near Winnipeg, who got dogs from Frank Engstrom of Minnesota and started their Gamefinder Kennel (The Leader Post, 1972; The Winnipeg Sun, 1982), Gary MacDonald with Kutya Kennel of St. Catharines, Ontario (The Hamilton Spectator, 1971), and Maria Sved with Farkasmajor Kennel of St. West, Vancouver, British Columbia (The Toronto Star, 1975).

A rare find was a story on the Annual House and Garden 1965 Tour sponsored by the Sherbrook Hospital Ladies' Auxiliary. This tour included four houses and one of them included a house that had all rooms with no less than five paneled in wood walls in each of them (Willard, 1965). It was the house of Ernest Gilbey, on Mountain Hill, Lennoxville, with a view of the Green Mountains of Vermont. The surprise find was a photo of a male Vizsla named Fritz that was a part of the trio pictured in front of a fireplace of the Gilbeys' living room.

Vizsla Club of Canada Formed

The Vizsla Club of America in the March 1963 issue of *The Vizsla News* issues their congratulations to the newly formed The Vizsla Club of Canada (p. 3). Its first Officers were Allen H. Todd of Calgary, Alberta (President), E. C. Laffin of Whitehorse, Yukon (Vice-President), Dr. A. Kemenes-Kettner of Calgary, Alberta (Secretary), Jessie M. Walker of Strathmore, Alberta (Treasurer), and D. C. Anglin of Calgary, Alberta (Solicitor).

The Hungarian National Kennel Club acknowledged the Vizsla Club of Canada's efforts by presenting them with the sculptor J. Kerenyi trophy - a bronze statue of an ancient Hungarian warrior. The first recipient of this trophy became *Can Ch Devecseri Somloi Pushi*, owned by Elizabeth Kemenes-Kettner (Strauz & Cunningham, 1973).

Canadian Vizslas Rock in Hunting and Field Trials

First field trials that involved Vizslas were held in the mid-1950th. A litter announcement published in *The Edmonton Journal* in 1956 stated the pups were "bred of proven hunters. Sire placed second in field trials. Be the first to own one of Canada's dark gold Vizslas" (p. 28). Field trials involving Vizslas were held near Ajax in Manitoba in 1959 (*The Globe and Mail*, 1959).

One of the first newspapers mentioning the Vizsla breed in relation to Canadian field trials occurred in 1958 and 1959. When the Toronto Branch of the Ontario Bird Dog and Conservation Association made a newspaper article about their September 27, 1959 field trial at Malton, next to the York Skeet Club, the article mentioned the success of the previous 1958 year trial. The German Short-Haired Pointer, Brittany Spaniel, Weimaraner, Pudelpointer, and Vizsla participated (*The Globe and Mail*, 1959).

In 1960, A. Gerle brought from Hungary a mature field-type female Vizsla, born July 27, 1956, named *Hun Ch Csikcsicsoe Ari-Nora*¹⁸ (Coffman, 1991, p. 18). During October 1959 in

¹⁸ *Csikcsicsoe Ari-Nora*, a female born in Hungary on July 27, 1956 (Sire: *Istvan's Ripp* and Dam: *Kati Jutka*), who had 30 offspring (Vizsla Database, n.d.).

Budapest, Hungary, in which 517 dogs including 72 Vizslas entered, Ari-Nora, handled by Lajos Dudas, was “twice winner,” first in her class in both the show ring and in the field (The Vizsla News, 1960, March, p. 5). Her photo appeared in this issue (p. 5). In the April 1960 issue of The Vizsla News, A. Gerle reported bringing Ari-Nora to Quebec, Canada (The Vizsla News, 1960, p. 6). Ari-Nora won several field trials including the Open Gun Dog and Open All-Stakes at the Quebec Pointing Breeds trial in 1962 (Strauz & Cunningham, 1973).

American Paul Sabo reported in the January 1961 issue of The Vizsla News on converting his new truck into a dog wagon and heading to Canadian Prairies in the Fall. He offered to take other Vizslas with him to field train them there (p. 8). Six Vizsla puppies (Sissy Selle litter born in January 1962), who P. Sabo took to Canada for the summer field training, did well in the Puppy Stake at the National Field Trial held at Bird Lane Farms on November 3 and 4, 1963 (The Vizsla News, 1963, March, p. 4; VanDivort, 1963). Every year during summer and early fall months, P. Sabo lived, trained, and hunted Vizslas in Ardath, Saskatchewan (The Vizsla News, 1964, July-August, p.10).

A Vizsla named *Can Ch, FTCh Rigo V Kline*¹⁹ placed fourth in the 1962 Open All-Breed Pointing Dog Field Trial at Ambleside, British Columbia (The Vancouver Sun, 1962). He was bred by Mildred Sullivan of Richmond, British Columbia and owned by R. Eugene Klein of North Vancouver, British Columbia. Rigo completed his show Championship in 1962 and was the first Vizsla to become a Dual Champion in 1965 when he completed his Field Championship title at the All Breed Pointer Club Field Trial in British Columbia on April 11, 1965. (The Vizsla News, 1965, October).

Doug Reynolds, “a trapshooting champ and lover of fine pointer dogs”, “wound up with a Hungarian Vizsla dog under a year old last month, took it hunting, was astounded at its

¹⁹ *Rigo V Kline*, a male born in Canada on December 18, 1959 (Sire: *Tito Of Shirbob* and Dam: *Donna Selle*), who had 31 offspring.

proficiency” (The Vancouver Sun, 1962, p. 27). Bill Sinster of Burnaby, British Columbia, was similarly excited about his 1962 goose hunting experience with his Vizsla near the Alberta-Saskatchewan border (The Vancouver Sun, 1962, p. 27). The Ontario Open Shooting Dog Championship for the Labatt Trophy and \$750 cash prize included Vizslas and occurred near the King Township Shooting Preserve near Nobleton on November 11, 1962 (Stonehouse, 1962).

Multiple winner (four times since 1961) of the Vizsla and All-Breed field trials in the United States was a Vizsla named *Am/Can FC Ripp Barat*²⁰, owned and handled by Betty Kenly, was trained by Paul Sabo in Canada. Ripp’s and his handler’s photos appeared in the September 1963 issue of The Vizsla News (p. 3), together with a letter from Betty Kenly announcing a partial retirement of the dog after his “fair share of wins” and to allow young generations to shine (p. 3). B. Kenly was right. Ripp’s puppies did well in the field. During field trials held by the Weimaraner Club of Alberta on September 15-16, 1963, Ripp’s puppies shined (The Vizsla News, 1963, October). P. Sabo reported that Rippy (*Am/Can FC Ripp Barat’s Rippy*²¹) was “extra good at 18 months” (p. 7). Rippy, owned by J. R. Holcomb and handled by Paul Sabo, took the second place in the All Age Shooting Dog Stake and in the Derby, to add to his previous wins in 1962 and 1963 (The Vizsla News, November, p. 18). Vizslas reported to participate at this prestigious field trial at the same location in September 1964 (Stonehouse, 1964). A photo of Rippy hunting in Canada appeared in the November 1965 issue of The Vizsla News (p. 8). In September 1964, Rippy won the Field Trial Championship in Craigdhu, Alberta, becoming the first Vizsla to win a Field Trial Championship in Canada (Jorgans, 1964). At this field trial, he completed his Canadian Field Trial Champion title.

²⁰ *Ripp Barat*, a male born in The United States on January 2, 1959 (Sire: *Broc Olca* and Dam: *Rata Z Povazia*), who had 119 offspring.

²¹ *Ripp Barat’s Rippy*, a male born in The United States on January 16, 1962 (Sire: *Ripp Barat* and Dam: *Sissy Selle*), who had 10 offspring.

The Canadian National Sportsmen's 1964 Show held in Toronto's 16-acre Coliseum (Stonehouse, 1964, March) saw more than 800 dogs with a total of 2,150 entries. The Vizslas participated in the indoor field trials during this event. At the 1965 National Sportsmen's Show, Dr. P.A. Wright shared the history of the Vizsla breed, described the Vizsla as "a very good all-round hunting dog" who also loves working in the water" and talked about his Vizsla *Can Ch Bakony Balatoni Katica*²²(Star Weekly, 1965, p. 34).

First National Field Trial was held in Craighdu, Alberta (near Calgary on the 7A Ranch) on September 26 and 27, 1964 (The Vizsla News, 1964, June, p.3). The same place hosted the Second Annual Vizsla Field Trial on September 25-26, 1965 (The Vizsla News, 1965, September). Paul Sabo handled both the first and second place winners, *Ripp Barat* and *Ripp Barat's Rippy*, in the Shooting Dog Stakes in September 1965 (Anderson, 1966).

On July 9, 1964, The Woman's Globe and Male mentioned a female Vizsla named *Penny Godollo*²³, owned by Marvin Hill of Clarkson, Ontario. M. Hill said his Penny was the best in the field work; she also had a litter of eight puppies earlier in March (The Globe and Mail, 1963, March).

A Vizsla named Fruzsi (*Bakony Betyar Fruzsi*²⁴), who placed in the Canadian field trials, reported to be glued to his favourite human, a toddler Cara Gorrill. Their photo appeared in the March 1965 issue of the Vizsla News (p. 9).

On July 12, 1969, The Globe and Mail ran a story on how to train puppies of pointing breeds, including Vizslas, by using a fishing rod (Stonehouse, 1969).

²² *Bakony Balatoni Katica*, a female born in Canada on December 24, 1963 (Sire: *Devecseri Somloi Pushi* and Dam: *Egerhegyi Tincsi*), who had 21 offspring.

²³ *Penny Godollo*, a female born in Canada on June 24, 1961 (Sire: *Fritz* and Dam: *Budavary Golden Panni*), who had 8 offspring.

²⁴ *Bakony Betyar Fruzsi*, a female born in Canada on June 27, 1963 (Sire: *Aprod Prucok* and Dam: *Golden Blitz Bakony*), who had 5 offspring.

One of Ross Eggstein's puppies appeared in a photo in the December 1965 issue of The Vizsla News covered with porcupine quills after a hunt in Canada (p. 12).

The Globe and Mail reporter Eldon Stonehouse, who covered stories on the field trials and tests in Ontario wrote an article explaining why pointing dogs including Vizslas were the best for "bobwhite" or quail hunting on the game farms (Stonehouse, 1968, p. 34). In 1968, the quail hunting occurred on the Hard Oil Shooting Preserve near Petrolia.

On October 19, 1969, the Goodwood Club held the North American Versatile Hunting Dog Association (NAVHDA) field trial in Goodwood, Ontario (Stonehouse, 1969, October).

In December 1969, The Globe and Mail covered a story about Leslie Takacs, who owned a sporting goods store on the West side of Toronto, getting a Hungarian import, a female Vizsla named Tucsok (cricket) (Stonehouse, 1969, December). Tucsok was of six-months age at the time the story was published. Takacs shared his experiences in getting his Vizsla puppy to learn English commands (she knew the Hungarians only when arrived) and train for hunting. He noted the dog was very smart and responded well to the soft training only.

Conclusions

During World War II the world almost lost the Vizsla breed and this period became known as one of the major bottlenecks in the breed's history. Those few Vizslas saved from the war ended up in other countries, many with their pedigrees lost during the escape. It made sense that Canada, who opened its borders to many nationalities including Hungarians, also welcomed Vizslas. Canada's rich lands and home to many game bird species were perfect for the Vizsla. Thanks to the dedication of many Vizsla supporters, the Vizsla (Smooth) was recognized as a breed in Canada a few years earlier than in The United States. The Vizsla as a breed not only survived in Canada, but the breed gained popularity in the show ring and in the field; Vizslas became family members in many Canadian homes.

This paper is a review of the newspaper and other archival records covering the early, pre-1969, history of the Vizsla in Canada. As more print materials become digitized, the author may discover additional stories and historical records. If that happens, the author plans on updating this paper with the new information as it becomes available.

References

- American Kennel Club. (2022). Vizsla history: The swift Hungarian hunting dog.
American Kennel Club,
<https://www.akc.org/expert-advice/dog-breeds/vizsla-history-swift-hungarian-hunting-dog/>
- American Kennel Gazette, June 1963.
- Anderson, F. (1966, March). The Vizsla Club of Canada,
https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1966_03_March_Vizsla_News.pdf
- Cook, M. (1958, April 28). Old English Sheep Dog wins best in show. The Montreal Star.
<https://www.newspapers.com/image/739693841/>
- Dawson, A. (1959, October 3). Manitoba hunting is fun: The prairie chicken is usually an impostor. The Globe and Mail, p. 25.
- Gerle, A.G. (1958, April). "New" breed for Canadian Sportsmen. Dogs in Canada.
https://www.ckc.ca/magazines/1958/1958_04_Kennel_And_Bench.pdf
- Hehr, M. (1964, November 4). Trainer's hands full with family of dogs. The Calgary Herald.
<https://www.newspapers.com/image/481196018/>
- Jorgans, B. (1964, October). Report of Canadian Vizsla National field trial. The Vizsla News,
https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1964_10_October_Vizsla_News.pdf
- Lee, B. (1960, July 16). Dogs achieve a new status in the home. The Globe Magazine, p.15.
- Nicholson, H. (1969, April 19). Kennel man discusses your dog.
<https://www.newspapers.com/image/1019418980/>
- Manitoba Free Press. (1866, April 26). Manitoba Field Trial Club.
<https://www.newspapers.com/image/65721518/>

Montreal Gazette. (1827, July 23). Nature reserved.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/705324696/>

Moshynska, O. (2019). Birth of the Vizsla. (3rd ed.). Zenodo,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14852821>

Moshynska, O. (2020, February 14). Link between the Huns and Vizsla dogs unravels an ancient enigma. Ancient Origins,

<https://www.ancient-origins.net/history-ancient-traditions/vizsla-0013289>

Moshynska, O. (2023). First Vizslas of The United States (2nd ed). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14903342>

Samedi-Dimanche (1958, April 16). Uniques au Canada, p.26.

Star Weekly. (1965, August 21). No mutts. <https://www.newspapers.com/image/992043484/>

Stonehouse, E. (1953). The dog in your family: Owner's ignorance is tough on pet.

The Globe and Mail, p. 26.

Stonehouse, E. (1959, October 3). Canine control officer necessary and useful. The Globe and Mail, p. 25.

Stonehouse, E. (1960, October 8). The dog in your family: Wonder dogs not so wonderful. The Globe and Mail, p.24.

Stonehouse, E. (1962, November 10). Dogs: Pointers are on trial. The Globe and Mail, p. 28.

Stonehouse, E. (1964, March 21). 2,150 entries means lot of noise. The Globe and Mail, p. 29.

Stonehouse, E. (1964, September 26). Dogs: Championship pointers. The Globe and Mail, p. 41.

Stonehouse, E. (1968, August 24). Dogs: Pointing breed best for bobwhite hunt. The Globe and Mail, T p.34.

Stonehouse, E. (1969, July 12). Dogs: Fishing rod helps train pointer, p. 35.

Stonehouse, E. (1969, October 4). Sporting breed club plans 1st field trial. The Globe and Mail,

p. 35.

Stonehouse, E. (1969, December 27). Dogs: Import from Hungary proves eager student. The Globe and Mail.

Straight, L. (1955). The Vancouver Sun. (1955, May 14). Vizsla – Latest wonder dog.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/492194009/>

Strauz John X. and Cunningham Joseph F. (1973). Your Vizsla. Denlinger.

The Calgary Herald. (1953, May 13). Immigrant professor is now hotel janitor.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/480846955/>

The Calgary Herald. (1956, August 24). Pet stock, birds.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/480884442/>

The Calgary Herald (1956, November 26). Dogs and pets.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/470903728/>

The Calgary Herald. (1957, February 13). Pet stocks, birds.

<https://books.google.ca/books?id=kWRkAAAAIBAJ&printsec=frontcover#v=onepage&q=vizsla&f=false>

The Calgary Herald. (1960, February 20). Dog show opens in the city.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/480890563/>

The Calgary Herald. (1960, April 14). Hungarian hunters.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/481307182/>

The Calgary Herald. (1965, March 1). Sluki judged best in city dog show.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/480859740/>

The Calgary Herald. (1966, March 8). A champ again. The Calgary Herald.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/481466839/>

The Edmonton Journal. (1956, November 22). Dogs and pets.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/470901911/>

The Edmonton Journal. (1959, May 28). This week's special.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/470270858/>

The Edmonton Journal. (1964, April 24). Dogs and pets.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/470839778/>

The Edmonton Journal. (2007, October 21). Special occasions.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/476772414/>

The Edmonton Journal. (2008, May 1). Obituaries: Kemenes-Kettner, Eizabeth.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/476184644/>

The Globe and Mail. (1959, September 12). Fast-flying Hungarians may be scarce this fall.

The Globe and Mail. (1963, March 29). Pet stock, p.47.

The Hamilton Spectator. (1971, September 24). Pet stock service.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/1015574767/>

The Leader Post. (1956, August 29). For sale. <https://www.newspapers.com/image/495074320/>

The Leader Post. (1972, May 6). Pets - Supplies,

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/495530832/>

The Montreal Star. (1958, August 14). Hungarian Vizsla.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/740000183/>

The Montreal Star. (1971, September 1). Pet & Supplies.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/742954942/>

The Ottawa Journal. (1965, May 1). Judges pick Peke as best in show.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/44453403/>

The Province. (1959, July 4). A boon to hunters.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/500942331/>

The Standard. (1998, June 6). Announcements: Deaths.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/1022400315/>

The Toronto Star. (1975, June 7). Pets & Pet Supplies.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/946450650/>

The Vancouver Sun. (1955, May 14). Vizsla – Latest wonder dog.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/492194009/>

The Vancouver Sun. (1959, January 17). Pet stock.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/492530939/>

The Vancouver Sun. (1962, May 15). Spaniel close to perfect in trials.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/492408222/>

The Vancouver Sun. (1962, August 28). Report banded blue grouse.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/492556948/>

The Vancouver Sun. (1962, November 7). Vizslas Vunderful says Doug.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/491678876/>

The Vizsla Club of America (n.d.). Retrieved on February 11, 2025,

<https://vcaweb.org/about-vizslas/vizsla-breed-history/>

The Vizsla News. (1960, March). Nominations,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1960_03_March_Vizsla_News_.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1960, April). Briefs,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1960_04_April_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1960, August-September). The oicture in the attic,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1960_08-09_August-September_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1961, January). Facts and figures,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1961_01_January_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1963, March). Vizsla Club of Canada,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1963_03_March_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1963, May). Vizsla wins group in Canada,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1963_05_May_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1963, July-August). Dear editor,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1963_07-08_July-August_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1963, September). Editor's note,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1963_09_September_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1963, October). Vizslas in Canada,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1963_10_October_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1963, November). At stud: Ripp Barat's Rippy,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1963_11_November_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1964, June). Fall field trials plans.

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1964_06_June_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1964, July-August). Dear editor.

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1964_07-08_July-August_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1965, March). One picture worth 1000 words...

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1965_03_March_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1965, September). Vizsla Club of Canada,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1965_09_September_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1965, October). News from Canada.

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1965_10_October_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1965, November). Vizsla Club of America, Inc: Field trial,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1965_11_November_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1965, December). One picture worth 1000 words...

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1965_12_December_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1967, August-September). Vizsla Club of Canada,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1966_08-09_August-September_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1967, October). Some pictures of the 1967 Vizsla Specialty winners.

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1967_10_October_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1968, January). Ch. Count Jonish Mignotte.

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1960-1969/1968_01_January_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Vizsla News. (1980, May). Vizsta's Jolla,

https://vcaweb.org/wp-content/resources/VizslaNews/1980-1989/1980_05_May_Vizsla_News.pdf

The Woman's Globe and Mail. (1964, July 9). Rare dogs and cats.

The Windsor Star. (1933, May 27). Rare breed increases U.S. canine ranks by half-dozen.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/500298881/>

The Windsor Star. (1956, March 6). In hound class.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/501477650/>

The Winnipeg Evening Tribune. (1933, May 27). The Magyar plays his part well.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/37263143/>

The Winnipeg Evening Tribune. (1959, November 14). Flight from Reds led to capitalism, p.5.

The Winnipeg Sun. (1982, March 29). Pets & livestock.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/735107620/>

Times Colonist. (1962, May 23). Nanaimo show: Victoria dog near perfect.

<https://www.newspapers.com/image/50678961/>

VanDivort, V. V. (1963, April). National field trial, November 3-4. The Vizsla News, pp. 11-13.

Vizsla Canada. (n.d.). The Smooth Vizsla. <https://vizslacanada.ca/436-2/>

Vizsla Database. (n.d.) <https://www.vizsladatabase.com/index.php>

Willard, G. (1965, May 14). Gilbey home on Moulton Hill Road. Sherbrooke Daily Record, p.6.